

LANGUAGE OF SUCCES: THE ROLE OF ENGLISH IN INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS TRANSACTINS

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Annotation: In international business, language is not just a means of communication but a strategic resource. It can help secure a multimillion-dollar contract or, on the contrary, lead to failure. A single misinterpreted expression, inaccurate translation, or inappropriate tone can influence on partner’s decisions and even damage. This article will help you understand how knowledge of business English facilities deal-making and how avoid the mistakes.

Kea words: English, business, international language, language barrier, official language, translation mistakes, cultural differences.

English as the main business language. Nowadays, English is international language and holds a very important place as the language of diplomacy, trade and business. Even if corporations are not English natives, in 98% of cases, they uses this language for business and 90% of deals are conducted in it.

English barrier is one of the main obstacles to signing international agreements. International corporations such as Airbus, Honda, Rakuten, Nissan and etc. have made English the official language within the company.

Case: Rakuten-the company that required employees to speak English. In 2010, the Japanese company Rakuten (a kind of Amazon equivalent), introduced the “English only” requirement. Employees had two years to learn English; otherwise, they could forget about promotions. The reason? The company wanted to conquer

the global market and avoid issues with translations. As a result, within five years, international revenue increased by 40%.

When language mistakes cost millions. Mistakes in business English can cause significant damage to a company's image, financial performance and relationships with partners. Incorrect translation, improper use of terms or clumsy formulations can lead to serious costs. Let's look at a few cases:

KFS: "Eat your fingers". When KFC entered to Chinese market, their slogan "Finger-licking good" was translated as "Eat your fingers". Of course, such a translation scared off customers. The company had to quickly redevelop marketing strategy, which cost tens of millions dollars.

HSBC: "Do nothing". In 2009, the international bank HSBC launched a campaign with the slogan "Assume nothing". In some countries, this phrase was translated as "Do nothing". Customer's trust was damaged and the bank had to urgently change its strategy, which cost ten million dollars.

How to avoid language failures in business. Make language easier. Hard idioms, slang and cultural references can be misunderstood. Don't say: "Can we strike a deal that gives us a better bang for the buck?". Say: "Can we discuss the pricing flexibility?"

Check the translations. Automatic translators don't always convey meaning correctly. Better use professional services or native speakers.

Consider cultural differences. In different countries the same phrase can understood differently. For example: In Japan, "Yes" can mean "I hear you", not constant. In USA the word "Interesting" can mean that they don't like the idea but the person doesn't want to say "No".

Use diplomatic language. Diplomacy is important in business English. Politely: "We may need to explore other options". Sharply: "That's not possible".

Language manipulations in negotiations. Sometimes the negotiators consciously use language to gain advantage. Let's break down several techniques:

1. Make illusion choice. If the partner want to lower the price, you can say: "Would you prefer a discount on bulk orders or extended payment terms?". A person has to choose one option, not just claim a discount.
2. Intentional pauses. In business English, the silence is powerful tool. For example, if after the price offer to be silent 5-10 seconds, the interlocutor can himself offer a concession.
3. Questions instead of assertions. "How do you see this proposal fitting your needs?"- makes partner think. "This proposal is perfect for you"- sounds obsessive.

Influence of non-verbal communication in English. Words is not all. In international negotiations tone, gestures and even the speed can play a decisive role.

- Americans speak quickly and clearly, waiting straight answers.
- British often use irony and veiled phrases.
- Asians appreciate pauses and avoid harsh answers.

Case: Why did Amazon fail in India? Amazon used aggressive marketing in India but failed to consider that local business owners prefer personal meetings and trust over formal contracts. As a result, local company like Flipkart outperformed them.

In conclusion. Language is not just a means of communication but a crucial tool in international business. Companies with a strong business English skills secure profitable deals, avoid financial losses and operate effectively in the global market.

What should you do to avoid all kinds of mistakes?

- Learn key business phrases.
- Considered cultural communication nuances.
- Analyze language manipulation in negotiations.

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